

Uber Driving Global Disruption: A study using SWOT and PEST framework

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Abstract

With the latest technological evolution, the world is moving faster than before in all sections of life to meet customer needs. One of the best innovations is Uber (ride sharing innovation) which disrupted the world by its technological landscaping and ease of use technology touching both developed and developing worlds. This paper is highlining the journey of Uber, its progress, and how the company is planning to grow in its journey going forward. Like any other company, Uber is dealing with many challenges and legal issues, and this paper is showcasing SWOT and PEST framework to study Uber's car-for-hire industry analysis.

Introduction

Uber was founded in 2009 out of customer frustration with the taxi business. Taxies were dirty, not well maintained, and hard to get when you needed one. Garrett Camp and Travis Kalanick commissioned a smartphone app intended to allow the consumer to hail a car with the push of a button instead of standing outside and hoping an empty taxi drives by. Something needed to change, and the market was primed for disruptive technology.

The Car-for-hire market exists primarily in large urban areas where it is cost-prohibitive to own, park, and insure a car, and it is highly regulated. The number of taxis available at a given time is limited, and the cost to operate a cab is very high. This leaves drivers with the incentive to maximize their return by concentrating on high traffic areas and times of the day, leaving less busy locations or times underserved.

We recommend that Uber begin to market its product. While word of mouth is a tried-and-true method of getting their name out there, their business model is to swoop in on a city and be fully established before the legislature has time to react. Because Uber feels it is essential to quickly build a loyal customer base using a focused advertising campaign, setting up at a new location would pay benefits (Kopp et al., 2015).

Secondly, because of Uber's repeated and ongoing legal issues when moving into a new market, they should consider lobbying the government to update the regulations in their favor before the powerful taxi lobby influences laws against their business model.

Finally, Uber's business model relies on drivers licensed by the city or state they work in. In contrast, their chief competitor in the car-for-hire business uses drivers from the general public using their cars. Uber should consider buying or partnering with Lyft to cover markets where they are not successful in entering. This type of brand management can enable Uber entry into markets that are resistant to their primary business model. If Uber follows these recommendations and others detailed in this document, it will have continued market growth and stability.

Milestones

The San Francisco-based Uber Technologies Inc. is an American multinational online transportation network company. It develops, markets, and operates the Uber mobile app, which allows consumers with smartphones to submit a trip request which is then routed to Uber drivers who use their cars. As of May 2016, this 6year old startup has already developed a niche for itself. The rise of companies like Uber and Lyft changes how the taxi business is carried out in this 21st Century and provides enough employment opportunities worldwide. Below are a few of the milestones this young company has achieved.

- Uber was founded in San Francisco, in 2009, by Garrett Camp and Travis Kalanick.
- In 2010 Uber raised \$1.25 Million in angel investments for initial investment.
- June 2010 started in San Francisco. May 2011 New York. By April 2012, they were in 7 cities.
- The October 2010 City of San Francisco issued a cease-and-desist order on Uber that threatened a \$5,000 fine for each instance and 90 days in jail for each day the company continued to operate. They disputed for three years, and the charges were dropped due to strong public demand.
- 2011 Washington DC Taxi Commissions drafted legislation that forced Uber to be priced 5X a cab. Uber created a campaign and asked the public to sign a petition and email council members to protest the legislation. The ruling was removed thousands of emails later, and a new bill passed that exempted Uber from taxi regulations.
- Uber's competitor Lyft was launched in 2012. It was a ridesharing App, and by 2014, it was in 60 cities.
- They started as limousines only. In 2012 Uber X allowed vehicles like Toyota Prius and SUV. In 2014 drivers can use sedans like Camry and Honda Accords.
- Uber was initially more expensive than regular taxis, but they reduced their prices to be more competitive and even cheaper in some cases.
- 2013 Uber secured \$2.5 billion in outside finance so 200,000 drivers could buy their own Uber cars at low-interest rates.
- 2014 Seattle Council passed an ordinance that limited the number of Uber drivers to 150. Uber gave a third party \$400,000 the next day, collecting and submitting 36,000 signatures to the city. The City Council voted in July 2014 and legalized Uber.

- On June 12, 2014, European cities, including London, Lyon, Madrid, and Milan, protested Uber, stopping in the middle of the street and shutting down major roads. After this, London's Uber ridership rose by 850%.
- 2014 Uber secured \$1.2 Billion funding and was valued at \$18.2 billion
- 2014 Uber was in 130 cities in 36 countries, and revenues were "at least doubling every six months."
- 2015 Uber raised an additional \$1.6 billion in convertible debt from wealth management clients of Goldman Sachs to be used for "Strategic Investments."
- Christmas 2015, after six years of business Uber, reached one billion rides.
- June 2016, just six months later, the company has announced that they have completed their two-billionth ride.
- 2016 they provided an average of 5.5 million rides a day, or 230,000 an hour, to hit a billion rides in six months. This company has been in business for the last six years but has expanded to 73 Countries, 450+ Cities, and over 2,000,000,000 rides (Tepper, 2016).

Industry Analysis

SWOT Analysis:

a. **Strengths**

Uber exists because of the shortcomings in the car-for-hire market. Their greatest strength is the inability of their competitors to meet customers' needs reliably and safely. The technology used to hail an Uber driver can be replicated by others, but the limits put on their competitors by government regulations are the forces that create the conditions Uber is exploiting to sustain their competitive advantage. Another strength of Uber is the trust and safety of its transactions. Since the rates are calculated and paid through the App, there is no opportunity for Wiley drivers to take them on a longer route to inflate the fare, and no cash exchanges hands, relieving drivers of the

burden of carrying large sums of cash, making them targets for robbery. This extra layer of safety attracts both drivers and riders to their business. Lastly, Uber's unapologetic tenacity in the face of growing legal challenges is a great strength.

b. Weakness

While Uber has many strengths, one weakness is its drivers. Technology can only go so far as to impress clientele. The drivers are the face of the company to their customers. Uber makes its drivers pass a background check; however, several high-profile issues of Uber drivers doing illegal things while on the clock. These include Jason Dalton, the Kalamazoo Michigan Uber driver who picked up fares between shooting sprees where he killed six people. Mr. Dalton told the police the Uber app took over his mind and body and made him go on the shooting spree. While there are mentally ill people everywhere in the world, Uber's responsible for the safety of its passengers, and high-profile problems like this counteracts the benefits. Another weakness is the legal opposition to their business model. While what they do is legal, there is a general feeling they are taking advantage of a legal loophole (Huet, 2015). While widely accepted by the underserved public, the taxi lobby is powerful, and they see Uber as cutting in on their lock on the business. They will be working hard to close the perceived legal loophole that Uber is taking advantage of. Uber needs to have a solid lobby to ensure any legal changes are in their favor.

c. Opportunity

Uber can revolutionize the taxi business, both from a customer and legal perspective. With the public aligning behind Uber, demanding better service, and being willing to pay for it, Uber can set the market price. They are already using analytics to set surge prices during high traffic, such as significant events or weather. With the Uber app loaded on each customer's phone, they have access to a considerable amount of data specific to each customer, including times they are active, things they are interested in, and events nearby their location if done correctly. Uber could use

analytics to market directly to its customers through the App. They could suggest events, movies, or even know when the customer typically goes shopping and indicate a car is available. Being a technology company, they should concentrate on using all of the technology at their disposal to build their competitive advantage. Imagine instead of hailing the cab on the street corner, the cab calls you.

d. Threats

There are three main Threats to Uber as we see it. The first is legal. While Uber has successfully defended its business model from litigation, it is generally believed that Uber is taking advantage of a loophole in the law. Legislators may write a law-making what Uber does illegal. If this happens, they will very quickly be out of business. The second threat is competition from copycat companies such as Lyft. Lyft does not use the same legal loophole, but instead, it is more of a trustworthy peer-to-peer business where individuals can choose to give rides to others using the service. This model may not be as legally risky and could be much harder to challenge. The final threat to Uber's business is autonomous driving vehicles. Google famously has several cars driving around America. Tesla Motors is experimenting with something similar called "auto-pilot ."The days of having a driver for this type of transportation are numbered, and Uber must respond to this, or its entire business could go the way of the dodo bird.

3.3 PEST (Political, Economic, Social and Technological) Analysis:

a) Political Analysis:

Governments around the world are reasonably antagonistic towards Uber's operational model. The rising corruption and red taping are hurting Uber's global expansion plan, and they are imposing a mandatory commercial licensing program for Uber vehicles. Lobbyists and local

politicians highly influence the legal system. Political pressure is high on the minimum wage determination for Uber Drivers or the Taxi industry. All those above factors negatively affect Uber's profit margin and brand image.

b) Economic Analysis:

As an effect of 'The Great Recession and 'Eurozone crisis,' the unemployment rate was high in recent years, and people were more conservative on spending during the last few years. That still creates pressure on Uber's expansion strategy. But China and India's high GDP growth rate and low-cost labor force are driving factors for its high growth in both these countries. Though these markets are very cost-sensitive, increased urbanization and modern lifestyle favor Uber's business model.

c) Social-cultural Analysis:

The population density in cities increases and people follow a high-paced modern lifestyle. So, to adjust and sustain this lifestyle, people need better and more cost-effective transportation facilities (Kopp et al., 2015). So, Uber's plan to provide better and more effective transportation is getting approval from the middle economy classes. This innovative hire-to-ride technique is fulfilling the urban customers' contemporary demands. But, as Uber App has a tracking facility, people are complaining that Uber is tracking their day-to-day behaviors, which is not acceptable as per a societal norm.

d) Technological Analysis

In this intelligent world, everybody uses smartphones and manages a mechanical life. As a result, now more than 4 billion smartphones are there globally and 6.6 billion internet users. This new trend gives Uber a technical advantage to popularize its app-based business model. The market is opening daily with better communication, and Uber is gaining more as per the First-To-

Market strategy. But it needs continuous innovation and acquisitions to be the market leader and to have long-term sustainability.

(Fig-1 PEST Analysis-Uber)

Current and future challenges

After going through the case study, one can completely agree that Uber is potentially far more than just a ride-for-hire service. It's a state-of-the-art logistics company with the ability to digitally connect people and move both people and products from one place to other. The concept behind the innovative App is like social media marketing and digital trafficking. Though the current market valuation puts the company at a staggering 40 billion dollars, this technological giant has never been a smooth journey. This car-booking company always has an on-road and off-road knack for riling up the taxi industry, often responding with protests, lawsuits, and bans throughout its global operations (Sugden & Malhotra, 2015). In 2015, numerous questions swirled around Uber,

its operation model, and its future expansion strategy. Bellow, we have conversed on Uber's current and future challenges, followed by recommendations on how the company plans to deal with these challenges in detail.

a. Legal Challenges:

Regulation is a constant challenge for Uber. As it becomes more popular, Uber will become subject to more legal and regulatory requirements common to other big businesses. For instance, the Americans with Disabilities Act is becoming a challenge for Uber. Since the Uber service is usually operated within a driver's vehicle, many vehicles are not wheelchair friendly. Taxi lobbies are also pressuring local governments to block Uber in many cities. They claim that Uber hurts their businesses and has an unfair advantage as Uber drivers are not subject to the same restrictions as licensed taxi drivers. Cities have acted against Uber by blocking ordinances that provide a path to legalization for mobile ride-booking apps and issuing cease-and-desist orders. Some US airports, such as Salt Lake City, have restrictions on Uber (Lydia, 2015). In addition to having an unfair competitive advantage, another accusation levied against Uber is that it does not adhere to proper safety standards. Uber drivers were involved in three rapes in Delhi, India; Chicago; and Boston. These rapes have harmed Uber's reputation and cast its safety into serious question. Few other lawsuits on Uber alleged that its drivers are distracted using the UberX App and causing accidents. Once again, this brings up the issue of how much Uber should be responsible for its drivers, and it calls them "independent contractors." Although Uber's website claims that it offers \$1 million in liability insurance plans for its drivers, some states are issuing warnings stating that insurance will not cover the rideshare type of accidents because personal cars are used for commercial purposes. Many states in the United States are reconsidering insurance requirements

in light of this issue, and insurance firms such as Geico and MetLife have begun offering insurance packages for ridesharing services.

b. Tax Disputes:

The next challenge that Uber faces relates to the employer-employee relationship. As many legal bodies dismiss Uber as a technology company, governments can argue that the entire ride payment is revenue for Uber and subject to city and state taxes, which Uber is not paying as per the state and federal regulations. Uber already faces strong complaints from various governments that it evades its tax liabilities onto its drivers and that the drivers are often non-compliant about paying their taxes. More tax legislation could exacerbate the problem and mean either an increase in ride fares or the end of Uber operations in that city, state, or Country.

c. Technological Challenges:

This innovative company always needs the right talent at the right time. Uber must understand its target market and maintain a solid technological and marketing mix to succeed. Uber's products are all digital, and consumers download Uber's App onto their smartphones. With this highly changing technological world, mobile technologies are changing fast, and Uber needs to match that for better customer experience and support (Kopp et al., 2015). Uber is also attempting to expand into other services. Its UberRUSH App launched in New York is used for package deliveries. UberFRESH and UberEATS are meal delivery apps that partner with local restaurants to offer meals to consumers within 10 minutes. It is also jumping to the driver-less car technology market, competing with Google and Apple. Though these new services are allowing Uber to branch out and expand its services into different businesses, it forces Uber to focus on constant innovation and applied knowledge. But with, the rising labor

cost and lack of enough talent in the market are going to give a tough time for Uber in the long run.

d. Expansion Challenges in Asian Market:

After USA, India, and China are the second and third largest markets for Uber. But the government red-taping and local political pressure are giving this company a hard time expanding its business smoothly in those markets. India rejected Uber's application for a taxi license. In New Delhi, a woman's rape allegation led to a ban against app-based services without radio-taxi permits in the capital. Hiring less educated drivers without adequately verifying their backgrounds caused such heinous offenses (Rai, 2015). In response to the alleged rape, Uber began installing the 'panic button' and tracking features. Uber also began offering its service in New Delhi without charging booking or service fees. Despite these changes, Uber continued to run afoul of Indian authorities. India asked Internet service providers to block Uber's websites because it continued to operate in the city despite being banned. However, it did not restrict the apps themselves because doing so would require it to institute the ban across the entire country (Rai, 2015). Uber must tread carefully to seize upon opportunities in India and China without violating regulatory requirements. This is more difficult as Uber drivers are independent contractors who set their schedules and decide whether to work or not (Sugden & Malhotra, 2015).

e. Competition from the Rivals:

The main competitors for Uber-Company include Lyft, Sidecar and Taxies (in the USA), Ola (in India), and Didi Chuxing (in China). Lyft and Sidecar, same as Uber, use innovative phone applications for their services and operate in approximately 200 cities in the US. They receive funding from venture capitalists and threaten Uber's competition in both tangible and intangible

service segments. Lyft thoroughly screens its drivers to ensure they are of acceptable age and are not prone to alcohol and drug abuse. The company also faces some regulatory restrictions on its operations. The prices of this company are very competitive compared to those of Uber.

Unlike Uber, the Taxi market does not offer specialized or booking services; their payment method is defined by queuing. Payments are made directly to the passenger, have no passenger rating mechanism, and wholly own their cars. While Uber surges prices in times of high demand, the Taxi responds by charging other fair (Horwitz, 2014). They both meter their fare based on time and distance. Though this Taxi market lacks technological innovation but takes advantage of local authorities and state laws, they are still tough competition to Uber.

f. Internal Challenges-Driver Satisfaction:

Uber operates in an industry where trust between strangers is vital. This trust ensures a safe and comfortable ride for both passenger and driver. Uber has developed a rating system to help assure this trust and reliability between passengers and drivers, called a rideshare rating system. Rideshare rating systems pose a unique challenge for Uber because of the way they are set up and the level of rider objectivity (Satariano, 2016). Uber's insistent policy of maintaining a five-star fleet can put drivers at a disadvantage. Uber rivals have similar policies; for instance, Lyft tells customers that anything less than five stars indicates unhappiness with the ride. Low driver scores can mean drivers are forced to take remedial classes to learn about safe driving techniques and driver etiquette—those who fail to increase their scores risk suspension or permanent deactivation. Because consumers have different views of what constitutes quality, it can be argued that Uber drivers are placed at the mercy of the consumer's mood. Drivers have also expressed unhappiness with Uber's pay. Uber will often lower fare rates to gain a competitive advantage in different

markets, cutting into driver earnings. Additionally, drivers drive their cars and spend their funds on insurance. As the company calls them independent Contractors instead of giving them employee status, Uber loses complete control, which is not a positive sign for a car-booking company.

g. Developing countries and Uber's pricing strategy:

As Uber expands outside the United States, it increases its operational risks. In Asia, the ratio of taxis to the population is higher than in America. Because of this, there is more competition between Uber drivers and traditional taxis. Furthermore, taxi service in Asia is fast, clean, cheap, and, in some countries, can be paid via Near Field Communications (NFC) cell phones - negating Uber's competitive advantage of being able to pay for a ride with its App. So, in Asia, Uber faces high pressure regarding its pricing strategy (Horwitz, 2014). As the Asian and South American market is very price-sensitive due to the sizeable middle-class population, Uber must provide more discounts and other benefits to attract local customers. Uber's surge pricing has led to considerable criticism in some situations in these markets.

h. Challenge of going Public (Issuing its First IPO):

Though there is consistent pressure from different sources and investors to make this company public and release its long-awaited IPO, Uber is still avoiding this perceptively. Its CEO Travis Kalanick made it clear that he avoided a big-time investor "exit"-an IPO-like the plague. This company is very close to his heart, and he wants to keep it private and continue focusing on innovation, avoiding a clash with rivals. Also, as the company can raise easy external funding and is valued at little more than \$50 billion now, it does not feel the heat of going public. The ride-hailing company's latest infusion of cash of record \$3.5 billion from Saudi Arabia's sovereign wealth fund - means Chief Executive Officer Travis Kalanick has the finances in hand to continue

avoiding a listing of his company any time soon. But as the competition in this industry segment is challenging day-by-day and as records indicate that in the first two quarters of 2015, Uber was reported to have lost \$1.7 billion and \$1.2 billion revenues, respectively, it is just a matter of time to watch how soon it is going to offer its first listings (Horwitz, 2014).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Uber has come a long way since 2009. Through their fearless way of doing business, they have created a niche in the global market. However, the market changes constantly, and to maintain a competitive advantage, Uber must respond to the challenges lying ahead of it.

Uber's main competitor is Lyft, which uses a similar technical App and business model like Uber. Uber can cut down the competition by dropping prices than its competition offers (already applied this tactic previously, but for a short period). Uber's financial position and cash flow are more substantial than its rivals to sustain the blow of price drop to acquire the business in developing countries, even for a more extended period. Uber can also acquire Lyft and other small growing companies such as Sidecar. This can also prove a beneficial strategy for Uber to keep its monopoly in the hire-a-ride market.

Currently, Uber uses real-time data through an app to locate and book cars for customers to be available "as soon as possible. "Uber can exploit the opportunity to "book cabs" for customers who know their schedule in advance, such as customers heading to a meeting, the airport, etc. This will help Uber make its operation efficient for customers with available plans and increase its customer base to avoid last-minute problems.

Uber's global popularity has grown exponentially due to its easy-to-use business model. But the controversies surrounding it can tarnish the reputation of Uber and can potentially harm its business and give an edge to its competitors. Hence, Uber needs to take immediate steps to fix

its reputation that has been tarnished due to the involvement of its drivers in criminal activities in different countries—installing a "panic button" and "tracking facilities" are not enough measures to make the customer feel secure. They can deploy serious background checks for their drivers to ensure that the riders are safe (Tepper, 2016). Also, like Lyft, they can use the customer rating system to drop or keep drivers. The success of the Uber business depends mainly on its drivers, making them an asset for Uber. To use these assets productively and maintain control of their drivers, they need to implement a more exhaustive 'training and evaluation program' for their drivers, which assess them on their ethical, behavioral, and presence of mind aspects. This will help Uber create a competitive workforce and prove a competitive advantage for them in the long run.

Uber can also grow internationally by customizing its pricing strategy based on the Country. Countries like India and China constitute 36% of the world's population; thus, Uber can generate significant revenue streams from these countries. The middle class comprises the most crucial working portion in these countries. Accordingly, Uber can offer discounts and low-cost rides to promote and establish its brand to target the middle-class population. Also, in these developing countries, the GPS is still evolving, which will increase the responsibility of Uber to make sure that the drivers have upgraded the GPS in their devices. Thus, to succeed in developing countries, they have to build a robust GPS in countries that lack the required infrastructure.

Meeting the legal and regulatory requirements has been a constant challenge for Uber. Uber has been fearlessly making its way through these challenges. However, Uber can create solutions to address some of these problems, such as the American act for Disabled. Uber can deploy cabs in significant cities suitable for disabled people to respond to these regulations. They can introduce the feature "cabs for disabled" in their App to understand the demand for such cabs in big cities

and slowly expand it based on the need. This will also create a competitive advantage for Uber over its competitors (Huet, 2015).

Uber has changed the face of the cab industry by combining technology with the hire-a-ride industry. The new wave of the driverless car can also impact the cab industry. Hence, with a long-term view, Uber can invest more money in forming alliances with companies that support driverless car technology, such as Tesla, Google, Apple, etc. Also, they can come up with advanced apps that share the same technology/concept with other services like heavy machinery, trailers, moving companies (i.e., Uber trucks), food delivery, etc. (Horwitz, 2014).

Currently, Uber accepts payments through credit cards. It can go for vertical integration by forming alliances with online paying systems such as PayPal, Payza, etc. This will increase Uber's operation efficiency, expand the customer base, and provide options to customers for payments. They can also invest in improving the safety standards of their cars to ensure safety for drivers and customers. These recommendations will help Uber create a short-term and long-term competitive advantage. Uber can expand its business through vertical integration and generate goodwill by controlling its business aspects.

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